

COMPARISON OF SELECTED PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS BETWEEN PRANAYAMA PRACTICED AND NON - PRANAYAMA PRACTICED MEN

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to comparison of selected physiological parameters between pranayama practiced and non- pranayama practiced men. To achieve this purpose of the study only sixty men students were selected from the Pachaiyappa's College for Men, Kanchipuram, Tamil Nadu were selected. Among them thirty pranayama practiced and thirty non- pranayama practiced men were selected as subjects respectively. The following variables namely resting pulse rate and breath holding time were selected as criterion variables. The data were collected from pranayama practiced and non- pranayama practiced men on resting pulse rate and breath holding time by taking radial pulse and holding the breath for time respectively. The independent 't' ratio was used to analyze the significant difference if any between groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance which was considered as an appropriate. The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between pranayama practiced and non- pranayama practiced men on selected criterion variables namely resting pulse rate and breath holding time.

Key Words: Radial Pulse Rate, Breath Holding Time, Pranayama Practiced, Non Pranayama Practiced

Introduction:

The three Sanskrit words Prana, Pran and Pranayama come from the same Sanskrit root 'pran' which represents the life force, the universal energy. These three concepts and the realities they represent from a continuum in which human beings are indissolubly linked to the divine source of cosmic energy.

The science of breath is called in Sanskrit *pranayama*. The word *pranayama* is a compound word which consists of *prana* and *yama*. *Prana* means life-force, or the vital energy, or that force by which we have our life. *Ayama* means control, i.e. control of the breath. That is the literal meaning. The first expression of life-force or *prana* is in the motion of the lungs. If a child does not breath attar its birth for some time, we give up the hope of that child. The first expression of life would be the breath, and motion of the lungs produces the breath. It is the primary function, and all other functions of the heart, digestive organs, and others are secondary.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to comparison of selected physiological parameters between pranayama practiced and non- pranayama practiced men. To achieve this purpose of the study only sixty men students were selected from the Pachaiyappa's College for Men, Kanchipuram, Tamil Nadu were selected. Among them thirty pranayama practiced and thirty non- pranayama practiced men were selected as subjects respectively. The following variables namely resting pulse rate and breath holding time were selected as criterion variables. The data were collected from pranayama practiced and non- pranayama practiced men on resting pulse rate and breath holding time by taking radial pulse and holding the breath for time respectively. The independent 't' ratio was used to analyze the significant difference if any between groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance which was considered as an appropriate.

Analysis of the Data:

The mean, standard deviation and "t" ratio values on resting pulse rate of pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced men have been analyzed and presented in table 1.

Table 1: The Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' Ratio Values Between Pranayama Practiced and Non - Pranayama Practiced on Resting Pulse Rate

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' Ratio Value
Pranayama Practiced Men	68.11	2.45	2.89*
Non Pranayama Practiced Men	72.04	2.01	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table value required for significance at .05 level of confidence with df 58 was 2.002).

The table 1 show that the mean values on resting pulse rate for pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced men were 68.11 and 72.04 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio value on resting pulse rate 2.89 which was greater than the table value required for significance with df 58 was 2.002.

The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced men on resting pulse rate.

The mean, standard deviation and "t" ratio values on breath holding time of pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced men have been analyzed and presented in table 1.

Table 2: The Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' Ratio Values Between Pranayama Practiced and Non - Pranayama Practiced on Breath Holding Time

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' Ratio Value
Pranayama Practiced Men	50.02	1.88	3.01*
Non Pranayama Practiced Men	42.81	2.11	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table value required for significance at .05 level of confidence with df 58 was 2.002).

The table 1 show that the mean values on breath holding time for pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced were 50.02 and 42.81 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio value on breath holding time 3.01 which was greater than the table value required for significance with df 58 was 2.002.

The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced men on breath holding time.

Conclusions:

Based on the results of the study, the following conditions were drawn.

- There was a significant difference between pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced men on resting pulse rate.
- There was a significant difference between pranayama practiced and non - pranayama practiced men on breath holding time.

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